

*Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge,
H2020*

D3.6: Music classifier models (V1.0)

Deliverable information	
WP	WP3: Mining Musical Patterns
Deliverable dissemination level	PU Public
Deliverable type	Software
Lead beneficiary	UNIBO
Contributors	CNRS, CNAM, KCL, NUIG, OU, SORBONNE, KNAW
Document status	Final
Document version	V1.0
Date	March 1, 2024
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004746

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Project Information

Project Start Date: 1st January 2021
Project Duration: 40 months
Project Website: <https://polifonia-project.eu>

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2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.6, titled *Music Classifier Models*, is slated for completion in Month 36. This deliverable is intricately linked to Task 4 of WP3: *Music Classification from Musical Patterns*. The leadership for this task rests with UNIBO, and active participation is expected from collaborating institutions: OU, NUIG, CNRS, and CNAM.

Task 4, led by UNIBO, is pivotal in the broader context of the project. The task revolves around the creation of a network of musical patterns interlinked through meaningful ontological relations. This network is instrumental in the classification of pieces of music (or their segments) based on various dimensions. The utilisation of extracted patterns and their relations as features for classifiers is a key focus, aiming to discern aspects such as genre, origin, and time of musical pieces.

An essential aspect of this task is its role in cross-validating classifications obtained from the analysis of textual resources in WP4. By validating results through this approach, the project gains a robust framework for assessing the efficacy of the patterns extracted in earlier tasks.

This deliverable builds upon the groundwork laid by previous tasks, particularly D3.1 and D3.2, which focused on open-source software for pattern extraction and the analysis of music repositories to identify patterns. D3.6 represents a significant advancement, contributing to the overarching objective of integrating extracted patterns into the classification of music objects. Like its predecessors, the document is structured into an introduction and literature review, followed by chapters corresponding to the main strands of parallel research, and concludes with a brief summary.

Document History

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) - Institution
V0.1	01/12/2023	Outline released.	James McDermott (NUIG) and Andrea Poltronieri (UNIBO)
V0.2	15/01/2024	Partial draft of intro and literature review.	James McDermott (NUIG) and Andrea Poltronieri (UNIBO)
V0.3	01/02/2024	Initial complete draft.	James McDermott (NUIG) and Danny Diamond (NUIG) and Peter van Krannenburg (KNAW) and Jacopo de Bernardinis (KCL) and Andrea Poltronieri (UNIBO) and Albert Meroño Peñuela (KCL) and Nicolas Lazzari (UNIBO)
V0.4	11/02/2024	Complete draft ready for internal review. Added statements on FAIRness and reproducibility as well as updated tables including details on software details and external links.	As above.
V0.5	21/02/2024	Added Conclusions including future work and exploitability, in NUIG chapter.	As above.
V0.6	29/02/2024	Added corrections and improved as suggested by the internal reviewers in all sections.	As above.
V1.0	01/03/2024	Submission to EU.	UNIBO

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1 Introduction

Music, as an art form, is incredibly diverse, spanning countless genres, styles, and cultural influences. With the proliferation of digital music platforms and the exponential growth of music libraries, the need for effective methods to classify and organise music has become increasingly vital. Music classification refers to the process of automatically categorising music into distinct genres, styles, moods, or other attributes based on its audio content, musical content or associated metadata.

Audio signal-based classification focuses on analysing the raw audio waveform, extracting features that capture the spectral, temporal, and timbral characteristics of music. This approach directly reflects the sonic content of music pieces, enabling classifiers to discern subtle nuances in performance, instrumentation, and production techniques [1]. In contrast, symbolic classification operates on symbolic representations of music, such as MIDI (Musical Instrument Digital Interface) or sheet music, which encode musical notes, rhythms, and structure. Symbolic classification provides a more abstract representation of music, facilitating analysis at the level of melody, harmony, and musical form [2].

In this deliverable, we explore three distinct types of classification methodologies developed within Work Package 3 (WP3) of the Polifonia project.

Section 2 focuses on tune family detection in Irish traditional music, identifying tune families within a corpus of Irish traditional tunes through new quantitative similarity methods. Leveraging melodic patterns and n-gram analysis, the classifier models uncovers recurring motifs and structures inherent to Irish traditional music.

Section 3 delves into harmony-based music classification, highlighting algorithms implemented within Harmory, a Knowledge Graph (KG) of harmonic patterns linked by similarity information, for harmonic music similarity and classification. By segmenting chord progressions and quantifying their similarity, Harmory providing classifiers with discriminative capabilities crucial for recognising resemblances among musical compositions.

Finally, Section 4 introduces ontology-based music classification, presenting *sandra*, a neuro-symbolic reasoner enabling inference of possible perspectives for interpreting music data. This approach allows the formalisation of musicological theories using a Description and Notation Scheme (DnS) ontology, with experiments conducted using conflicting theories such as roman numeral analysis and cadences as defined by Zarlino, showcasing the versatility and adaptability of the framework.

2 Tune Family Detection in Irish Traditional Music

ID	https://zenodo.org/records/10697952
Type	Software
Title	FONN - FOlk N-gram aNalysis
Credits	Danny Diamond (NUIG) and James McDermott (NUIG) and Mathieu d'Aquin (NUIG)
Description	Software for mining patterns in musical corpora - with tune family classifier models as an application
Source Code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/folk_ngram_analysis
Documentation	README.md
Release	Version 2.0.1
Licence	MIT
Running Instance	GitHub: demo notebooks
Bibliography	<i>Tune family detection in a corpus of Irish traditional dance tunes</i> , Danny Diamond, 2024. MSc Thesis, University of Galway. In preparation.
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4, D3.5, D5.6

ID	https://zenodo.org/records/10697952
Type	Data
Title	Tune Family Annotations
Credits	Danny Diamond (NUIG)
Description	Annotations of tune family membership for a small subset of <i>The Session</i>
Source Code	GitHub: tune_family_annotations directory
Documentation	README.md
Release	Part of: Folk n-gram Analysis Version 2.0.1
Licence	CC-BY
Running Instance	See FoNN demo notebooks above.
Bibliography	<i>Tune family detection in a corpus of Irish traditional dance tunes</i> , Danny Diamond, 2024. MSc Thesis, University of Galway. In preparation.
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4, D3.5, D5.6

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter we describe work on classifying tune families in Irish traditional music.

The central research question is: is it possible to identify tune families in a corpus of Irish traditional tunes via new quantitative similarity methods informed by work in the fields of computational musicology, MIR, and by the study and practice of Irish traditional music?

The body of this chapter is extracted from the draft MSc thesis of Polifonia/NUIG researcher Danny Diamond, which is forthcoming in the middle of 2024. Moreover, some aspects of the work have been described in previous Polifonia deliverables, D3.1-D3.5. This information will be only briefly summarised here. Discussion of the final methodology and results has not been presented in previous Polifonia deliverables.

Tune families are a central concept in the musicology of folk music, as described in more detail in Section 2.2. Creating classifier models for tune families is important, because once such models are validated, they can serve to identify unknown tune family members. This is especially valuable in an oral tradition, where informal transmission of tunes can lead to incomplete identification of known tune families. In a modern incarnation of the oral tradition, *The Session* is a crowd-sourced website where practitioners upload tunes and tune variants. At around 40,000 tunes, and growing quickly, automated methods of identifying tune family members are required. The datasets we use, extracted from *The Session* and then augmented with ground truth tune family membership, are described in more detail in Section 2.3.

Based as it is in WP3 (Mining Musical Patterns), the classifier models we create start with the concept of melodic patterns, in particular n -gram patterns. Several approaches to defining and using patterns are investigated, as described in Section 2.4. Baseline methods (not using patterns directly) are also described. Detailed experimental results are described in Section 2.5.

In the final section, we briefly report on FAIRness and reproducibility.

2.2 Related Work

The existence of common melodic patterns between tunes in the Irish tradition was first noted in general terms by 19th century collectors George Petrie and William Forde [3]. The influential Irish-American music collector Francis O'Neill devoted a chapter in his 1913 book *Irish Minstrels and Musicians* to the qualitative identification of related melodies within the Irish tradition [4].

In 1950, American folk music collector and researcher Samuel Bayard published his theory of *tune families*: proposing that many traditional melodies could be traced across space and time, in the manner of a family-tree, to “ur-melodies”, i.e. prototype melodies [5]. In Bayard’s words:

“...a group of melodies showing basic interrelation by means of constant melodic correspondence, and presumably owing their mutual likeness to descent from a single air that has assumed multiple forms through processes of variation, imitation and assimilation.”

Bayard’s tune family concept has been widely adopted in research on Irish and other Western folk music [3, 6, 7].

2.2.1 Structural analysis of Irish music

The importance of accented tones (i.e. the notes ‘on the beat’) as an important element in defining a stable outline melody crops up consistently in the literature [6, 8, 9, 10]. Ó Suilleabháin’s writings on the importance of these *set accented tones* in defining tune melodies is central to our work [6]. The incipit or opening motif is also of prime importance in defining the melody of a tune [6, 11], as well as the first cadence usually occurring in bars 7-8.

2.3 Data

We derive our data from the website thesession.org (*The Session*) [12]. It consists of a discussion forum, discography, performance listings, and a crowd-sourced corpus focused on the Irish traditional instrumental dance repertoire. As *The Session* is crowd-sourced, contributors to the corpus are free to upload unique variants for each tune, and it is not unusual for individual tunes to have upwards of 10 variants.

2.3.1 Tune family ground truth

The methodology applied to ground-truth annotation of *The Session* began with a survey of relevant printed sources, some already cited. All references to tune families and/or similarities within the Irish tradition were noted, which yielded a total of 115 potential tune families. A subset of 21 of these potential families were chosen, with priority being given to the oldest and most extensive families. These 21 families were then cross-referenced against studies relating to British and North American folk music to identify families which co-occurred in these related traditions. Following the writings of Bayard [13], Bronson [14], and Cowdery [15] we hypothesised that families presenting with the broadest and most varied forms across multiple traditions constituted the oldest and most fundamental tune families. Such families were deemed most important for inclusion in our ground truth.

One of the authors (DD), an expert practitioner of Irish traditional music, manually checked all occurrences, eliminating doubtful family members and small families. Where necessary the author played tunes on fiddle directly from the score to inform judgement of tune family membership. In contrast to a typical machine learning labelling/annotation process, where multiple annotations with high inter-annotator agreement are required, this annotation process starts with the academic literature followed by detailed investigation per tune by an expert practitioner. Therefore, multiple annotations are not required. The end result is a set of 314 tune variants spread across 10 families, containing a range of tune types and time signatures broadly representative of the corpus as a whole.

The resulting dataset is available as a csv file: https://github.com/polifonia-project/patterns-knowledge-graph/tree/main/P2KG-Pipeline/inputs/thesession_annotated_subset/metadata with an open license.

2.4 Tune Family Classification Methodology

Our high-level approach to tune family classification is to use tune similarity. Given a tune in a family, we detect members of the same family by ordering all other tunes in the corpus by similarity to that tune. Depending on the application, we can then either impose a threshold in terms of similarity, or in terms of rank; or we can iterate through the ordered tunes, investigating each one further by listening to confirm or disconfirm its membership, until we decide there are no further viable candidates. All of these methods are suitable for different applications. For our purposes, we will measure the performance by measuring the number of false positives in the first n ordered candidates, as described later. Therefore, for the remainder of this section we focus on tune similarity.

We have defined several methods for calculating tune similarity. All begin with preprocessing steps which result in a tune being represented as a sequence of diatonic scale-degree integers. There are three variants of this sequence:

- Note-level: every note in the tune, whatever its duration or metric strength;
- Accent-level: based on the musicological theory of *set accented tones*, described above, this sequence keeps only notes which occur on strong beats;
- Duration-weighted: as an alternative method of dealing with note duration, this method stores one integer for each beat.

Sequences were normalised by subtracting the key centre, so that all tunes were effectively in the same key.

For the purposes of this work, a pattern is defined as a sequence of diatonic scale degrees between 3 and 12 elements in length, which occurs at least once in any tune in the corpus. For each tune in the corpus, each of the three sequence variants was calculated, and for each value $3 \leq n \leq 12$ any subsequence of length n occurring more than once in the corpus becomes a pattern.

For a subset of n values, $6 \leq n \leq 12$, TF-IDF values [16, 17] for each pattern occurrence in each tune were calculated. These TF-IDF values give a numerical expression of the local prominence of each pattern within each tune, while normalising out excessively frequent ‘stop word’ patterns. Where a pattern does not occur in a given tune, its TF-IDF value is 0.

For the core task of tune family detection, three approaches to melodic similarity have been developed:

- *Motif*: this approach begins by extracting prominent local patterns from a query tune, according to their TF-IDF values. For each of these search term patterns, similar local patterns in other tunes across the corpus are discovered via a custom-weighted Hamming distance [18]. Tunes are ranked according to the number of similar patterns they contain and additional weightings are applied as described below, outputting a weighted count of similar patterns per tune, which is taken as a tune similarity score.
- *Incipit and cadence*: incipit and cadence subsequences (see Section 2.2) extracted from each tune are compared via Levenshtein distance [19] and ranked by similarity.

- *TF-IDF*: a vector representing TF-IDF values for every possible pattern ($6 \leq n \leq 12$) was formed for each tune. Pairwise Cosine similarity was calculated between TF-IDF vectors for all tunes in the corpus. This is intended as a relatively simple and computationally efficient baseline metric.

As this is a software deliverable, we omit full details of the workings. Readers can see the MSc thesis (already cited) of author DD, and/or the well-commented code at the URL already cited.

2.4.1 Measuring tune family classification performance

For each approach to tune similarity described above, we apply it to each of the 314 annotated tune family members versus all 40k The Session tunes, ranking them by similarity. This enables calculation of Average Precision. In fact, we calculate three Average Precision (AP@k) values for each results table: AP@1, AP@5, and AP@10. AP@k values calculate the proportion of true vs false positive results at every results ranking between 1 and k, then average these values to provide a single output value. AP@1 simply detects whether or not the top-ranked similarity result is a true positive. AP@5 and AP@10 respectively return the average proportion of true positives in the top 5 and 10 ranked results.

2.5 Results

For the *motif* method, two methodological variants were tested, motif 1.1 and motif 1.2 – full details are in the cited MSc thesis.

Both variations on the *motif* method were applied on *note-level*, *accent-level* and *duration-weighted* *n*-gram pattern inputs for $n=6, 8, 10$ and 12 , giving a total of 12 experimental results sets for each of *motif 1.1* and *motif 1.2*. Results were also calculated for the *incipit-cadence* method and the *TF-IDF* method, with variants based on the sequence type (*note-level*, *accent-level*, or *duration-weighted*). The *incipit-cadence* and *TF-IDF* methods do not require multiple values of *n*.

Both methods exhibit similar MAP values, with *motif 1.2* performing slightly better overall for $n=6$ and $n=10$, and *motif 1.1* performing slightly better overall for $n=8$ and $n=12$. A clear trend can be observed in the precision values: MAP increases with *n* for both methodological variants.

The best results based on the above are from the *motif 1.1* methodology, as applied to 12-gram patterns extracted from the *accent-level* feature sequence input data. Accordingly, this results set is retained for comparison and analysis versus the outputs of the *Incipit and cadence* and *TF-IDF* methodologies, which we investigate next. They are given in Table 2.3.

In Table 2.3 it can be observed that the *TF-IDF* method outperforms the *incipit and cadence* method according to all precision metrics with the exception of MAP@1 for *duration-weighted* input data.

In Table 2.4 we can see that the *incipit and cadence* method performs best for *duration-weighted* input data while the *TF-IDF* method performs equally well for both *note-level* and *accent-level* inputs. Referring back to Table 2.3, we can see the MAP@1 and 5 values at *note-level* are clearly

	n=6	n=8	n=10	n=12
	Accent-level			
MAP@1	0.305	0.479	0.543	0.615
MAP@5	0.210	0.300	0.368	0.414
MAP@10	0.140	0.204	0.248	0.287
	Note-level			
MAP@1	0.086	0.498	0.581	0.608
MAP@5	0.083	0.295	0.347	0.365
MAP@10	0.065	0.204	0.238	0.247
	Duration-weighted			
MAP@1	0.197	0.552	0.590	0.623
MAP@5	0.114	0.327	0.367	0.382
MAP@10	0.079	0.230	0.250	0.253

Table 2.1: MAP@1, 5 and 10 values for 12 similarity experiments. The *motif 1.1* variant was applied to all combinations of input data representation (*note-level*, *accent-level* and *duration-weighted*) and *n*-gram pattern length ($n=6 \dots 12$) for every tune in the annotated subset of *The Session*. The highest values of MAP@1, MAP@5, and MAP@10 are highlighted.

	n=6	n=8	n=10	n=12
	Accent-level			
MAP@1	0.340	0.492	0.546	0.613
MAP@5	0.215	0.305	0.369	0.413
MAP@10	0.144	0.207	0.251	0.285
	Note-level			
MAP@1	0.095	0.498	0.584	0.613
MAP@5	0.084	0.290	0.348	0.359
MAP@10	0.067	0.198	0.236	0.245
	Duration-weighted			
MAP@1	0.225	0.540	0.594	0.627
MAP@5	0.129	0.327	0.369	0.387
MAP@10	0.088	0.226	0.250	0.261

Table 2.2: MAP@1, 5 and 10 values for 12 similarity experiments. The *motif 1.2* variant was applied to all combinations of input data representation (*note-level*, *accent-level* and *duration-weighted*) and *n*-gram pattern length ($n=6 \dots 12$) for every tune in the annotated subset of *The Session* corpus. The highest values of MAP@1, MAP@5, and MAP@10 are highlighted.

higher than their *accent-level* equivalents. Based on the information provided by both tables, we selected the *duration-weighted incipit and cadence* results and *note-level TF-IDF* results for further analysis alongside our previously-selected *motif* results.

	Incipit and cadence	TF-IDF
	Accent-level	
MAP@1	0.629	0.717
MAP@5	0.405	0.511
MAP@10	0.263	0.370
	Note-level	
MAP@1	0.632	0.765
MAP@5	0.372	0.529
MAP@10	0.241	0.366
	Duration-weighted	
MAP@1	0.721	0.717
MAP@5	0.483	0.492
MAP@10	0.331	0.345

Table 2.3: MAP@1, 5 and 10 values for 6 similarity experiments, in which the *incipit and cadence* and *TF-IDF* similarity methods are applied to (*note-level*, *accent-level* and *duration-weighted*) input data representations for every tune in the 314-tune ground-truth annotated subset of *The Session* corpus. For each method, the highest values of MAP@1, MAP@5, and MAP@10 are highlighted in green.

2.5.1 Results Summary

In Table 2.4, we show a summary of results from different methods. We now averaged across the MAP@1, 5 and 10, to achieve summary results. We can see that the *motif* results are more accurate than the *incipit and cadence* results for *accent-level* and *note-level* inputs but are outperformed by the *incipit and cadence* results at *duration-weighted* and by *TF-IDF* for all inputs. We also see that *motif 1.1* was better than *motif 1.2* on two of the tree representations (rows in the table).

	Incipit and cadence	TF-IDF	Motif
Accent-level	0.432	0.553	0.439
Note-level	0.415	0.553	0.407
Duration-weighted	0.511	0.518	*0.419

Table 2.4: Aggregated MAP (average of MAP@1, 5 and 10 values) for all similarity experiments using the *TF-IDF* and *incipit and cadence* methods. Corresponding values for the best-performing *motif* results are included for comparison. The highest aggregated MAP values for each method are highlighted in green. Note: the *motif* values are for the *motif 1.1* methodological variant unless asterisked, in which case they represent *motif 1.2* results.

A much deeper analysis of the results, broken down by tune family, tune family size, and more, is also possible. As an example, we present Fig. 2.1 which shows results for the motif method only, broken down by individual tune and tune family. It shows that overall performance is better for

some families than others: for example, *Greig's Pipes*, *Road to Lisdoonvarna* and *The Blackbird* seem to present more problems for our method than other families. It also demonstrates an “all or nothing” pattern of performance, i.e. each tune is either quite successful in finding other tunes in the same family, or quite unsuccessful – with relatively little middle ground. This could suggest a target for future work.

Figure 2.1: Strip plot showing aggregated MAP for each of the 314 individual tune-level *motif* results sets, categorised by tune family.

2.6 Conclusion, Future Work and Exploitability

Overall, performance is good but there is room for improvement. Future work could involve alternative methods of combining patterns, and alternative weightings and weighting methods, to improve performance. The central motif methods presented here are not machine learning methods *per se*, but for example, the weightings could also be learned to try to optimise performance. An important application of this work will be to iteratively apply these methods to tentatively label other tune family members in the corpus. Each new tentative label will be tested by an expert listener. Confirmed matches will then go into the tune family, and will enable further new, unknown connections. A plan for future work is to iteratively expand the set of known tune families in this way.

Although we have focussed on a single dataset of tune families here, the methods are quite general and re-usable. All three methods provide a measure of dissimilarity between any pair of tunes. Thus, they can be re-applied without any new training phase to a new dataset of tune families. They can even be applied to other classification tasks, since any dissimilarity method can become a classification method via approaches such as k -nearest neighbours or support vector machines.

2.7 FAIRness and reproducibility

In this section we briefly report on adherence to FAIR principles of the tune family classification work.

As always, development is in the open, at the URL: https://github.com/polifonia-project/folk_ngram_analysis. This repository forms a component of the Polifonia ecosystem. We use open-source licenses and commonly-accessible data formats.

The new ground truth annotation is itself freely available under an open license.

A Zenodo release of the software has been made at the time of previous deliverables and a further release will be made to mark this deliverable.

We adhere to the Polifonia data management plan [20]. Under the DMP, *ethical use of data* is noted as important. Use of data from an oral tradition, such as the Irish traditional music represented in *The Session*, can be controversial. Many *The Session* contributors – musicians, who perhaps see themselves not only as musicians but as keepers of the tradition – have reacted negatively to use of data in AI applications, e.g. as we see on <https://thesession.org/discussions/47876>. However, here we make an important distinction. These musicians including the curators have reacted negatively to AI-generated tunes, and in particular to AI-generated tunes which purport to be “real”. In contrast, our work reported here is in musicology and music information retrieval, not in generation. While many musicians are indifferent to such applications, very few are against them.

3 Harmony-based Music Classification

ID	https://zenodo.org/records/8021211
Type	Software
Title	Harmory: the Harmonic Memory
Credits	Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL) and Andrea Poltronieri (UNIBO) and Albert Meroño Peñuela (KCL) and Valentina Presutti (UNIBO)
Description	Harmory is a Knowledge Graph of interconnected harmonic patterns aimed to support creative applications in a fully transparent, accountable, and musically plausible way. The software implemented for the realisation of Harmory includes state-of-the-art harmonic segmentation and harmonic similarity algorithm.
Source Code	https://github.com/smashub/harmory
Documentation	README.md
Release	V1.0
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Running Instance	Harmory Endpoint
Bibliography	J. de Berardinis, A. Meroño-Peñuela, A. Poltronieri, and V. Presutti, “The harmonic memory: a knowledge graph of harmonic patterns as a trustworthy framework for computational creativity,” in Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2023, 2023, pp. 3873–3882.
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.5, D5.6

3.1 Introduction

In this section, we describe work on Harmony-based Music Classification, focusing on the software proposed in *Harmory: the Harmonic Memory* [21].

The Harmonic Memory is a Knowledge Graph (KG) of harmonic patterns extracted from a large and heterogeneous musical corpus. By leveraging a cognitive model of tonal harmony, chord progressions are segmented into meaningful structures, and patterns emerge from their comparison via harmonic similarity. Akin to a music memory, the KG holds temporal connections between consecutive patterns, as well as salient similarity relationships. After demonstrating the validity of our choices, we provide examples of how this design enables novel pathways for combinational creativity [22]. The harmonic memory provides a fully accountable and explainable framework to inspire and support creative professionals – allowing for the discovery of progressions consistent with given criteria, the recomposition of harmonic sections, but also the co-creation of new progressions.

In the following sections, we delve into the algorithms implemented for harmonic music classification within Harmory, elucidating their functionality and significance within the broader context of music similarity and classification. The software developed within Harmory for harmonic segmentation and similarity computation constitutes a pivotal asset for the task of music classification, particularly in the domain of cover song detection. By adeptly segmenting chord progressions into coherent harmonic structures and quantifying their similarity, Harmory equips classifiers with robust features crucial for discerning resemblances and disparities among musical compositions. This proficiency in harmonic analysis and comparison furnishes classifiers with discriminative capabilities essential for accurately identifying cover songs, wherein subtle variations in harmonic patterns serve as distinctive markers.

Harmory represents a notable evolution from LHARP, as outlined in the Polifonia Deliverable D3.2 [23]. LHARP is a novel method for harmonic similarity analysis, that, similarly to Harmory, focuses on shared repeated patterns among symbolic chord sequences to enable explorative studies. However, the key departure between the two approaches lies in their respective methods for similarity computation. While LHARP leverages a novel similarity function to ascertain harmonic resemblances among symbolic chord sequences, Harmory adopts Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithms as the cornerstone of its similarity assessment. This transition from LHARP's bespoke similarity function to DTW algorithms in Harmory underscores a fundamental shift towards a more versatile and widely recognized approach in similarity computation. DTW algorithms offer distinct advantages, particularly in capturing subtle temporal variations and nuances within musical sequences, thereby enhancing the discernment of harmonic similarities.

3.2 Related Work

Harmonic progression serves as a fundamental component of tonal music composition across various musical styles and traditions. From a computational standpoint, the automated identification of shared harmonic patterns among musical pieces holds significant potential for supporting diverse applications, including information retrieval, cover song detection, music exploration, recommendation systems, and musicological analysis. Despite its wide-ranging utility, the development of novel algorithms for harmonic similarity has received limited attention in the past decade. The current state-of-the-art methods, pioneered by Baas de Haas, notably include the Tonal Pitch Step Distance (TPSD) [24] and the Chord Sequence Alignment System (CSAS) [25]. TPSD incorporates a perceptually and musicologically grounded distance function, while CSAS utilises string matching techniques to compute similarity scores between chord sequences or distances between chords and keys. Empirical comparisons between TPSD and CSAS, particularly in the context of cover song detection, reveal CSAS to exhibit superior performance, albeit with a more intuitive formulation and stronger musicological interpretation for TPSD.

Additionally, alternative approaches such as those employing generative grammars of tonal harmony have been proposed, offering formal descriptions of chord sequences [26]. However, limitations in the expressiveness of current grammars pose challenges for parsing certain chord sequences, thereby impacting the computation of harmonic similarities.

In addition to these methods, LHARP [23] offers a local approach for harmonic similarity, emphasising shared repeated patterns among symbolic chord sequences to accommodate a wide set of applications. LHARP’s local nature enables more explorative studies by unveiling and establishing links when local harmonic patterns are repeated in both sequences.

3.3 Methodology

The main steps for the creation of Harmory are illustrated in Figure 3.1, and encompass four stages: (i) projection of harmonic sequences in the Tonal Pitch Space; (ii) novelty-based segmentation of harmonic sequences; (iii) pattern identification through similarity-based linking of harmonic segments; and (iv) KG creation. For the purposes of this deliverable, our attention will be directed towards stages (i), (ii), and (iii).

Our workflow is defined from the harmonic analysis of a piece, which contains a sequence of *chords* in Harte notation [27], their *onsets*, and the associated local *keys*. Formally, let $\mathbf{c} = \{c_1, \dots, c_N\}$ denote a chord sequence of length N , where each chord figure c_i is drawn from the Harte chordal set $\mathcal{H}$. Similarly, $\mathbf{k} = \{k_1, \dots, k_N\}$ denotes the corresponding local keys of $\mathbf{c}$, s.t. each k_i is a tonic-mode tuple defined from $\mathbb{T} \times \mathbb{M}$, where $\mathbb{T} = \{Ab, A, A\#, Bb, \dots, G\#\}$ is the set of all possible tonic notes, and $\mathbb{M} = \{\text{major, dorian, } \dots, \text{locrian}\}$ is the set of all possible modes in Western tonal music.

For simplicity, chords are expected to be temporally aligned with their onsets, meaning that c_i ends when c_{i+1} starts, $\forall i \in N - 1$. Hence, *onsets* are defined as a $(N + 1)$ dimensional vector $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{R}^{N+1}$ to compensate for the end time of the last chord (t_{N+1} is the end of c_N). Onsets are given in seconds for harmonic analyses on audio music; or as global beats for symbolic music. For example, $\mathbf{c} = [G, B:\text{min}, E:\text{min}7, \dots]$, $\mathbf{k} = [(G, \text{major}), (G, \text{major}), (G, \text{major}), \dots]$, and $\mathbf{t} = [1, 3, 5, \dots]$ are the first three occurrences of such vectors for a “*A Day in the Life*” by The Beatles.

3.3.1 Encoding chords in the Tonal Pitch Space

Given a harmonic analysis $\mathbf{H} = \{\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{t}\}$, the first step is to encode $\mathbf{c}$ and $\mathbf{k}$ as a numerical stream, so as to allow the processing of similarity/distance operations. This is necessary because chords ($\mathbf{c}$) and tonalities ($\mathbf{k}$) are complex elements to process, and come in symbolic format. More specifically, a chord label is a convention for describing intervals built on a root note. For example, the label of a C major seventh chord ($C:\text{maj}7$) represents the intervals of a major quadriad with a minor seventh built on the note C , which is equivalent to the note set $\{C, E, G, Bb\}$. Also, the harmonic function of a chord is contextual to the global (and local) key [28].

One option here is to leverage Representation Learning methods on symbolic music to learn harmonic embeddings from a large corpus of chord sequences [29, 30]. These include static embedding methods, such as Word2Vec [31] and Glove [32], as well as sequence models for contextualised representations, such as ELMo [33] and BERT [34] – which have proved their effi-

Figure 3.1: Overview of the main steps for the creation of Harmory, from the encoding of chord progressions in the Tonal Pitch Space (TPS) and their segmentation, to the emergence of harmonic patterns through similarity and the creation of the KG.

cacy on a variety of natural language processing tasks. Nonetheless, in the music domain, representation learning methods have recently started to gain success for audio music [35], whereas little attention has been given to symbolic music. This is exacerbated by the challenge of finding musicological interpretability of the resulting embeddings, requiring new probing and evaluation methods for music [36].

We aim for an encoding of harmony that is well established, perceptually and musicologically plausible, and explainable by design. Hence, we rely on the Tonal Pitch Space [37] – a cognitive model of tonality used in music psychology and computational musicology.

The tonal pitch space

The *Tonal Pitch Space* (TPS) model [37] provides a scoring mechanism that predicts the proximity between musical chords. It is based on the Generative Theory of Tonal Music [38] and designed to make explicit music theoretical and cognitive intuitions about tonal organisation. The model works by comparing any possible chord to an arbitrary key, by means of the *basic space*. The basic space is constituted by five different levels, ordered from the most stable to the least stable: (i) the *Root level*; (ii) the *Fifths level*; (iii) the *Triadic level*; (iv) the *Diatonic level*; and (v) the *Chromatic level*.

Each level holds one or more notes, indexed from 0 (*C*) to 11 (*B*). The *Root level* holds the root of a chord (0 for C-major), while the *Fifths level* adds the fifth (0, 7 for C-major). The *Triadic level* has all the notes in the chord (0, 4, 7 for C major). The *Diatonic level* depends on the chord’s key as it holds all the notes of the diatonic scale of the key (0, 2, 4, 5, 7, 9, 11 for the C major key). Finally, the *Chromatic level* holds the chromatic scale (0-11).

The distance between two chords c_i, c_j in keys k_i, k_j is calculated using the *basic spaces* of the chords. The basic space is set to match the key of the pieces (level *iv*), and their levels (*i-iii*) are adapted to match the chords to be compared. The Chord distance rule is applied to calculate the distance. The Chord distance rule is defined as $d(x, y) = j + k$, where $d(x, y)$ is the distance

Figure 3.2: Example of Harmonic SSM resulting from the application of Equation 3.1 on the TPS signal of “Crazy Little Things Called Love” by Queen, using a sampling rate $f_s = 1$. Four main block-like structures are visible, correlating with the musical form of the piece. Smaller, nested harmonic structures of lower granularity are observed within these blocks.

between chord x and chord y ; j is the minimum number of Circle-of-Fifths rule applications to shift x into y , and k is the number of non-common pitch classes divided by 2 in the levels (i - iv) of the basic spaces of x and y . The Circle-of-Fifths rule consists in moving the levels (i - iii) four steps to the right or left on level iv .

For each comparison between two chords, the TPS returns a value in $[0, 13]$. TPS has been demonstrated to be sound both musicologically and perceptually [24, 39], and in this work, it is used to encode and compare chord-key pairs.

3.3.2 Novelty-based harmonic segmentation

The projection of chord-key pairs (c_i, k_i) in the TPS is a fundamental requirement to perform harmonic segmentation. First, the given harmonic annotation $\mathbf{H}$ is used to sample a signal $\mathbf{X}$ of length $d = t_{N+1} \cdot f_s$, where harmonic observation (c_i, k_i) is consecutively repeated $t_i \cdot f_s$ times (its duration), according to a sampling rate f_s . Each element $x_i \in \mathbf{X}$ now encodes an input for the TPS model, containing the harmonic content at the i -th sample.

The resulting signal allows for the computation of two harmonic descriptors, i.e., the *Harmonic Profile* (or TPS time series), and the *Harmonic self-similarity matrix* (SSM) – the entry point for segmentation. The former is defined as a vector $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ s.t. $q_i = \text{tps}(x_i, k_1)$, holding the TPS distance between each harmonic observation x_i and the global key k_1 of the piece (assumed as the first key occurrence). Similarly, the Harmonic SSM is a matrix $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ s.t.

$$\mathbf{S}(n, m) = 1 - \frac{\text{tps}(x_n, x_m)}{13}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $x_i \in \mathbf{X}$ is a column vector; $n, m \in [0 : d - 1]$; 13 is a normalisation factor (the maximum TPS value); and the subtraction from 1 is used to obtain a similarity score from a distance measure.

Self-similarity matrices have been extensively used for structure analysis, due to their ability to reveal nested structural elements [40, 41]. As can be seen from Figure 3.2, block-like structures are observed when the underlying sequence shows homogeneous features over the duration of the corresponding segment. Often, such a homogeneous segment is followed by another homogeneous segment that stands in contrast to the previous one.

To identify the boundary between two homogeneous but contrasting segments (2D corner points), we slide a checkerboard kernel $\mathbf{K}$ along the main diagonal of the SSM and sum up the element-wise product of $\mathbf{K}$ and $\mathbf{S}$. A checkerboard kernel can be simply defined as a box kernel $\mathbf{K}_B \in \mathbb{Z}^{M \times M}$ where $M = 2L + 1$ is the size of the kernel, defined by $\mathbf{K}_B = \text{sgn}(k) \cdot \text{sgn}(l) \forall k, l \in [-L, L]$, where sgn is the sign function. This yields a novelty function $\Delta_{kernel}(n)$ for each index $n \in [1 : d]$ of $\mathbf{X}$ as follows:

$$\Delta_{kernel}(n) = \sum_{k, l \in [-L, L]} \mathbf{K}(k, l) \cdot \mathbf{S}(n + k, n + l) \quad (3.2)$$

for $n \in [L + 1 : d - L]$. When $\mathbf{K}$ is located within a relatively uniform region of $\mathbf{S}$, the positive and negative values of the product tend to sum to zero (small novelty). Conversely, when $\mathbf{K}$ is at the crux of a checkerboard-like structure of $\mathbf{S}$, the values of the product are all positive and sum up to a large value (high novelty) [42].

Local maxima of the novelty curve are then used to detect the boundaries of neighbouring segments that correspond to contrasting harmonic parts. For this, we use a pick peaking method that applies a smoothing filter to the novelty function (to reduce the effect of noise-like fluctuations) and uses adaptive thresholding to select a peak when novelty exceeds a local average [43]. The detected segment boundaries are used to split $\mathbf{X}$ and the corresponding $\mathbf{q}$ into a number of non-overlapping harmonic structures. This yields $\bar{\mathbf{q}} = \bar{\mathbf{q}}^1, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{q}}^P$, where P denotes the number of structures.

3.3.3 Linking harmonic segments via similarity

Each harmonic structure $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i$ is then considered for harmonic similarity. Since $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i$ is still a time series (a partition of $\mathbf{q}$, the Harmonic Profile), we formulate the harmonic similarity between two harmonic structures by comparing their time series. This is done using Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) – an algorithm for comparing time series, which has been widely used across various domains, including speech recognition [44], pattern recognition [45], and bioinformatics [46]. In our case, DTW has desirable properties, as it is invariant to time shifts, and robust to local variations. Vanilla DTW compares two time series by calculating the cumulative distances between each point/observation. It allows for non-linear alignment between the time series by considering the local warping path. The cost matrix, holding the cumulative distance between each corresponding point, is constructed using the Euclidean distance, and is formalised as:

$$d_{DTW}(\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i, \bar{\mathbf{p}}^j) = \sqrt{\sum_{(v,w) \in \pi} \|\bar{q}_v^i + \bar{p}_w^j\|^2} \quad (3.3)$$

where π is the optimal warping path – the shortest cumulative distance between the time series (found via dynamic programming).

As the computational complexity of vanilla DTW is quadratic in the sequence length [47], here we use the *Sakoe-Chiba* variant. The latter achieves linear complexity $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot w)$, by constraining the warping path within a window of size w , rather than using all points (N).

Prior to the computation of similarities, time series are normalised and resampled to meet the same length, and standardised to zero mean and unit variance. This has the effect of comparing time series by looking at their shapes in an amplitude-invariant manner – which brings us closer to the identification of harmonic patterns.

The latter emerge after retrieving the k most similar structures for each segment $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i$, and applying a filtration to retain only those structures $\bar{\mathbf{p}}^j$ whose $d_{DTW}(\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i, \bar{\mathbf{p}}^j)$ is below a given threshold. Structures sharing the same (normalised) TPS time series ($d_{DTW} = 0$) define a distinct harmonic pattern; whereas segments with similar time series can be grouped within the same pattern family/cluster.

3.4 Evaluation

To validate Harmony, we tested the efficacy of the two central components underpinning its creation: the DTW harmonic similarity (Section 3.3.3), and the harmonic segmentation (Section 3.3.2).

3.4.1 Evaluation of Harmonic Similarity

We evaluated the DTW harmonic similarity by comparing our implementation with other algorithms for the *cover song detection* task – a common benchmark for similarity algorithms in the symbolic music domain [24, 39]. The task of cover song detection in Music Information Retrieval (MIR) involves identifying instances where one recording of a song closely resembles or is derived from another recording, often with variations in arrangement, performance, or interpretation.

In this comparison, performance is evaluated using two standard metrics: *First Tier* and *Second Tier*. The former measures the ratio of correctly retrieved songs within the top $(C_t - 1)$ matches to $(C_t - 1)$, where C_t is the size of the song class (e.g. the same composition, or performance) for track t . The First Tier can be formalised as:

$$FirstTier_{(D)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=0}^N \frac{\|L_{|(C_t-1)} \cap C_t\|}{\|(C_t - 1)\|}, \quad (3.4)$$

					Schubert		CASD		Schubert+CASD	
Algorithm	TPS Mode	Stretch	Constraint	Normalise	First Tier	Second Tier	First Tier	Second Tier	First Tier	Second Tier
TPSD	offset	-	-	-	0.49	0.63	0.62	0.68	0.58	0.67
TPSD	profile	-	-	-	0.53	0.74	0.76	0.83	0.69	0.8
DTW	offset	stretch	-	-	0.94	0.98	0.53	0.67	0.66	0.76
DTW	profile	stretch	-	-	0.97	0.99	0.6	0.69	0.71	0.78
DTW	offset	stretch	sakoe_chiba	-	0.96	0.99	0.62	0.7	0.72	0.79
DTW	profile	stretch	sakoe_chiba	-	0.97	0.99	0.69	0.77	0.77	0.84
DTW	offset	stretch	itakura	-	0.96	0.99	0.55	0.65	0.68	0.75
DTW	profile	stretch	sakoe_chiba	yes	0.97	0.99	0.7	0.76	0.79	0.83
LCSS	offset	-	sakoe_chiba	-	0.38	0.61	0.03	0.07	0.14	0.24
LCSS	offset	-	itakura	-	0.7	0.8	0.14	0.23	0.31	0.41
SoftDTW	offset	stretch	-	-	0.93	0.97	0.55	0.69	0.67	0.77
SoftDTW	profile	stretch	sakoe_chiba	-	0.98	0.99	0.62	0.73	0.73	0.81

Table 3.1: Performance of similarity algorithms on cover song detection. The highlighted lines denote the best performing algorithms, while results in bold indicate the best performance obtained for the *First Tier* and *Second Tier*, respectively.

where N is the set of all tracks in the dataset having at least a “cover”, and $L_{(C_t-1)}$ denotes the list of matches for track t ranked by similarity – where only the first $(C_t - 1)$ occurrences are considered. Similarly, the Second Tier is defined as the ratio of correctly retrieved songs within the best $(2C_t - 1)$ matches to $(C_t - 1)$.

$$SecondTier_{(D)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=0}^N \frac{||L_{(2C_t-1)} \cap C_t||}{||C_t - 1||} \quad (3.5)$$

3.4.2 Data

We compute and evaluate the harmonic segmentations on a dataset comprising 320 chord progressions, obtained from randomly sampling 40 pieces per audio partition in ChoCo (isophonics, billboard, casd, schubert-winterreise, rwc-pop, uspop-2002, jaah, robbie-williams). This yields a diversified (several genres, durations, etc.) yet representative sample of Harmory ($\approx 2\%$ of ChoCo); which prevents larger partitions from biasing the overall results. For $\mathcal{P}$, we assembled a dataset of known harmonic patterns from Impro-Visor [48], which is available on GitHub¹. After filtration of trivial occurrences (e.g. chord uni-grams, sequences with repeated chord occurrences, etc.), the dataset counts 300 unique patterns spanning from 3 to 10 chord occurrences per pattern (the length of a chordal pattern).

Methods. We compare our DTW similarity (c.f. Section 3.3.3) with the following algorithms for harmonic and time series similarity:

- **Tonal Pitch Step Distance (TPSD)** [24, 39], a state of the art method that measures the difference between the *Harmonic Profiles* (see $\mathbf{q}$ in Section 3.3.2) of the given harmonic sequences. The difference is determined as the minimal area between the two time series, after considering all possible horizontal shifts. TPSD can handle sequences of different

¹<https://github.com/Impro-Visor/Impro-Visor>

Figure 3.3: Structural coverage of known patterns for each segmentation method, using Equation 3.4 (left), and Equation 3.5 (right). Results are reported as distances averaged per pattern group (a group contains known harmonic patterns of the same length).

length, and has a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(nm \log(n + m))$, where n and m denote the length of the compared chord sequences [49];

- **Longest Common Subsequence (LCSS)** [50], a method expressing time series similarity based on their longest common subsequence. Similarity is calculated as the relative length of the longest common subsequence compared to the length of the shortest time series, thus ranging in $[0, 1]$. Using dynamic programming, LCSS is bounded in $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$;
- **Soft Dynamic Time Warping (Soft DTW)** [51], a variant of DTW that allows for non-binary (fuzzy) alignments between time series, by using a soft-constraint. Soft DTW can be computed with quadratic time/space complexity.

All experiments are performed on the Harmonic Profile, in addition to an alternative formulation of the TPS time series, called *offsets*, where $q_i = \text{tps}(x_i, x_{i-1})$ (chord offset distance).

For *DTW*, *LCSS* and *Soft DTW*, two types of constraints were also tested: *Sakoe-Chiba* and *Itakura*. Analogously to Sakoe-Chiba, the Itakura constraint sets a maximum distance for each point in the time series, making the algorithm more efficient, and reducing the risk of being trapped in local minima. Several parameter settings for the Sakoe-Chiba radius and Itakura band were tested, and the best results were obtained by setting them to 5 and 4, respectively. This parametrisation turned out to be optimal across all our experiments.

Each method was tested on sequences of original length (*no-stretch*) and after resampling to the shortest sequence. We also experimented with normalised time series (Section 3.3.3).

Results. Table 3.1 shows the results of this comparison and highlights the best performing algorithms. Results are presented for Schubert and CASD separately, and also in a third merged setup (Schubert+CASD). Notably, the performance of the DTW algorithm is significantly better for Schubert (one piece, multiple performances), while for CASD (one performance, multiple annotations), TPSD performs slightly better. The best results for the third setup are obtained using the Sakoe-Chiba DTW, using normalisation and resampling on the shortest sequence. It is also worth remarking that our implementation, besides being the most accurate overall, is also the most efficient approach, due to its linear complexity.

3.4.3 Structural coverage of known patterns

To validate our harmonic segmentation (Section 3.3.2), we measure the overlap between the resulting structures with a collection of well-known chordal patterns. This exemplifies the hypothesis that a good segmentation would maximise the “reuse” of harmonic patterns – as building blocks that can be found in other pieces.

Given a segmentation $\bar{\mathbf{q}} = \bar{\mathbf{q}}^1, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{q}}^P$ of a piece, with each $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i$ containing a TPS time series, the overlap of $\bar{\mathbf{q}}$ with a dataset of known harmonic patterns $\mathcal{P}$ is computed as:

$$o_M(\bar{\mathbf{q}}) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T \min_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}} d_{\text{DTW}}(\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i, \mathbf{p}), \quad (3.6)$$

$$o_B(\bar{\mathbf{q}}) = \min_{\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i \in \bar{\mathbf{q}}} \min_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}} d_{\text{DTW}}(\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i, \mathbf{p}), \quad (3.7)$$

which differ in the aggregation function. The former measures the average pattern distance contributed by each structure in the segmentation; the latter, instead, only retains the distance of the most similar pattern that was matched to one of the structures. When $o_M = 0$, all segments are fully matched/found in $\mathcal{P}$; whereas o_M is minimal when at least a segment matches a pattern in $\mathcal{P}$.

Methods. We compare our method (denoted as *harmov*) to fast low-cost unipotent semantic segmentation (FLUSS) [52] – a state of the art algorithm for time series segmentation defined on the Matrix Profile [53]. FLUSS annotates the time series with information about the likelihood of a regime change (a segment boundary); and is parameterised by a fixed window size m , and the number of segments to detect r . We also include a baseline splitting a time series in r uniform segments. Both methods operate on the TPS Profile of $\mathbf{h}$, and are optimised via grid search.

Results. The structural coverage, computed for each segmentation method and aggregated for all known harmonic patterns of the same length, is reported in Figure 3.3. For both measures o_M , o_B , the segmentations produced by our method (*harmov*) produce the lowest distances – meaning that they show the highest overlap with the known harmonic patterns in $\mathcal{P}$. This behaviour is preserved for all pattern groups (the x-axis), and the gap with the other methods increases with pattern’s length. The second performing method is FLUSS, using $r = 14$ split regions and a window size of $m = 3$. However, for longer patterns, the latter performs comparably with a fixed sequence split (the other baseline). Finally, it is worth remarking that results for all baselines are first optimised on a grid search; whereas we use the default parameterisation for *harmov*.

3.5 FAIRness and reproducibility

In this section, we briefly report on adherence to FAIR principles of the Harmory’s software components. The software implementation of Harmory is openly accessible through a GitHub repos-

itory², ensuring transparency and facilitating reproducibility of experiments and results.

The dataset used in our experiments is a subset of ChoCo [54], which is also open source and available under the CC-BY-SA-NC license³, ensuring accessibility and promoting reuse while maintaining appropriate attribution. Furthermore, we adhere to the Polifonia data management plan, ensuring proper documentation and management of data assets throughout the project lifecycle.

To enhance reproducibility, the codebase has been shared on Zenodo⁴, a platform for archiving and sharing research artifacts with persistent identifiers. Lastly, the paper describing Harmory's methodology and findings has been published in open access.

²<https://github.com/smashub/harmory>

³<https://github.com/smashub/choco>

⁴<https://zenodo.org/records/8021211>

4 Ontology-based Music Classification

ID	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10649490
Type	Software
Title	Ontology based music classification using sandra
Credits	Nicolas Lazzari, Stefano De Giorgis, Aldo Gangemi, and Valentina Pre-sutti
Description	Classify compositions from ChoCo by relying on a DnS ontology. De-veloped ontologies include roman numeral analysis and Zarlino’s ca-dence classification.
Source Code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-based-music-classification
Documentation	https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-based-music-classification
Release	https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-based-music-classification
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Running Instance	-
Bibliography	Nicolas Lazzari, Stefano De Giorgis, Aldo Gangemi, and Valentina Pre-sutti. (2024). Sandra – A Neuro-Symbolic Reasoner Based On De-scriptions And Situations.
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.5, D5.6

4.1 Introduction

In this Chapter we describe *sandra* [55]¹, a neuro-symbolic reasoner that allows the inference of possible perspectives from which data can be interpreted. Reasoning on perspectives is relevant in many contexts and applications. In very rigorous domains such as medicine or jurisprudence, the same case can be interpreted through more than one description: a patient’s situation can be analyzed through different diagnostic hypotheses; a legal state of affairs can be interpreted by applying different, possibly conflicting, norms. In storytelling techniques, spin doctors can frame the same topic in different ways to support alternative political scenarios: “*Conservatives claim that we need relief from taxes vs. Democrats claim that taxes are investments for us.*” [56].

Informally, a set of facts (situation) can be described through more than one - potentially conflict-ing - perspective, which can be inferred even in presence of partial data. This paper proposes

¹Work currently under review.

a method and a neuro-symbolic reasoner, named *sandra*, able to infer all perspectives that are plausible descriptions for a given situation. Associating different plausible descriptions to a situation requires the capability to reason at both the intensional and the extensional level (i.e. with both concepts and facts) posing a challenge on how to formally represent the knowledge required, as well as on the reasoning technique to apply. From a knowledge representation perspective, the Description and Situation (DnS) [57] ontology design pattern addresses this problem. DnS provides a formalization of frame semantics, generalizing over Fillmore’s [58] and Minsky’s [59] proposals. It has been largely used in many ontology projects (mainly using its OWL formalization) [60, 61, 62, 63]. DnS defines a general vocabulary for n-ary relations, introducing the concepts of *description* and *situation*. A situation is a set of facts, as it is described by an observer, involving a set of entities.

A description is a perspective (a theory, a schema) defining concepts that can classify, hence interpret, the entities observed in a situation. With DnS, both descriptions and situations are formalized as first-order entities in an ontology, therefore potentially enabling reasoning over them both at the intensional (description) and extensional (situation) level, in the same domain of discourse. In DnS terms, we say that a situation s satisfies a description d , when d is a plausible or correct interpretation of s . A perspective-based reasoner shall be able to infer all the possible perspectives even if they are incompatible (disjoint).

Figure 4.1: Example of two descriptions (*Commerce buy* and *Contest winning*) that are satisfied by a situation that involves the entities *Bob*, *ENCOM*, *Laptop*. The two descriptions define the same roles, hence they provide two different perspectives from which the situation can be interpreted.

To the best of our knowledge, this behaviour is unobtainable with existing logic-based reasoners. Within a traditional logic approach, conflicting concepts (such as *Commerce buy* and *Contest winning*) are correctly modelled as disjoint classes. Therefore, classifying the situation from the example of Figure 4.1 in both descriptions would lead to an inconsistency. Furthermore, no classification would be provided if the extensional data available is partial. Fuzzy reasoners, such as [64], may be more tolerant but would show the same problem (inconsistency) adding an

issue of possible undecidability. Logic-based representations and reasoning have also benefits: a clear, formal model of descriptions is defined and the inference is always sound and complete with respect to that model. At the same time, the data representing situations must be structured and compliant with such model, requiring significant effort.

Neural Network models are a solution to both obtaining an approximate classification, and being able to inject any type of data (images, text, etc.), not only structured data. Nevertheless, they may need a large sample including both descriptions and situations, and the results may be incompatible with the formal model, for example it might happen that only some of the plausible descriptions are retrieved. In short, logic reasoning lacks inconsistency and partial-data-tolerant deductions, while neural network models lack the completeness of deductive inference.

Neuro-symbolic methods, such as [65, 66, 67], combine important benefits of logic-based and approximate reasoning, and (very important) they can ingest unstructured data. Nevertheless, they rely on the same consistency assumption, which is undesirable in a perspective-reasoning scenario.

The approach proposed in this research (*sandra*) relies on the neuro-symbolic paradigm but addresses this issue. It formalizes and implements the inference of the `satisfies` relation between situations and descriptions and, at the same time, it provides a probability score and a deductive, interpretable inference.

It includes: (i) a theoretical framework formalizing DnS in a differentiable and probabilistic fashion, which we prove to be correct with respect to DnS. It creates a vector space V isomorphic to a DnS-based ontology (defining a set of descriptions); (ii) the implementation of a neuro-symbolic architecture, where the neural network is constrained to position any detected situation (from any source type) in one or more subspaces of V , each corresponding to a description defined in the ontology. The intuition is that this constraint makes the network less prone to noise. Our formulation allows efficient inference in the DnS domain. Our hypothesis is that by constraining the representation learning process to a DnS-based ontology we can perform perspective-based reasoning without performance loss or increase of computational complexity.

To evaluate our hypothesis we experiment our method on two different tasks: visual reasoning on the I-RAVEN benchmark [68] and domain generalization on Fashion-MNIST [69]. For each task, we assess the influence of adding *sandra* to a standard baseline model and find increased performances with polynomial complexity². A detailed description and analysis of the experiments can be found in [55]. In Section 3.3 we show how *sandra* can be used to classify chord sequences from ChoCo [70].

4.2 Related Work

The idea of using geometric representation for cognitive theory was originally proposed by Peter Gärdenfors [71] as an intermediate representation layer between sub-symbolic and symbolic knowledge. A conceptual space depicts concepts as convex regions. Each region is shaped

²in time and space with respect to the number of entities within an ontology.

by the attributes that characterise that concept. Our method follows the intuition of conceptual spaces. Two main problems on conceptual spaces are highlighted by [72]. One is the derivation of region-based representations for concepts that is difficult when data comes from real-world scenarios; another issue is that the representations in conceptual spaces are not amenable to expressing relational knowledge. Given the integration of a neural network as a situation approximator, as proposed in Section 4.4.6, and the Dns formalization (Section 4.3), our method overcomes both limitations. Other approaches that implement conceptual spaces, such as [72], propose to interpret embeddings as conceptual spaces. Others approximate ontologies based on their graph representation or rely on specific neural architectures, like Logic Tensor Networks to obtain deductive inferences [73, 74]. Differently to these approaches, our representation is not an approximation of the ontology. The ontology is used to obtain a vector space in which concepts are represented. This is similar to the approach described in [75], where geometrical properties are exploited to obtain sound knowledge representation methods.

Other related approaches integrate symbolic representations in geometrical spaces to support reasoning such as in [66] where the authors complement Answer Set Programming with neural networks; in [65] ProbLog is extended to the use of neural predicates; and [67] implements approximate logical inference. These approaches are inherently dependent on probabilistic logic, suffering from a lack of inconsistency tolerance.

In the musical domain, approaches that rely on ontologies to classify music have been proposed with promising result, such as relying on the combination of Context Free Grammars and Ontologies [76] or implementing an ontology using Object Oriented Programming [77].

4.3 The Description and Situation Ontology Design Pattern

Figure 4.2: Examples of some descriptions and situations alongside the conversion of a situation into V to detect the satisfied descriptions. The process of deducing which descriptions are satisfied by f_s is shown on the right.

In the Description and Situation (DnS) ontology design pattern, descriptions and situations are n-ary relations. We refer to the arguments of a description as *roles*, and to those of a situation as *entities*. For example, in Figure 4.1, *Business*, *Consumer*, and *Item* are the roles of the

Commerce buy description, while `ENCOM`, `Bob`, and `Laptop` are the entities of the situation s_1 . A situation s satisfies a description d , if each entity of s can be classified by one role of d ³. For example, s_1 satisfies `Commerce buy` as `Business` classifies `ENCOM`, `Consumer` classifies `Bob`, and `Item` classifies `Laptop`.

A formalization of DnS in First Order Logic is given in [57]. We extend it to allow roles as n-ary relations and provide here the resulting formal semantics. With $\mathcal{O}$ a DnS-based ontology, we define $\mathcal{D}$ as the set of descriptions in the ontology, with $\mathcal{R}$ the set of roles and $\mathcal{E}$ the set of entities and assume that $\mathcal{D} \cup \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{E} \subset \mathcal{O}$.

Definition 1. A description d is a tuple $d = (r_1, \dots, r_n) \in \mathcal{D}$ with $r_i \in \mathcal{R} \cup (\mathcal{D} - \{d\})$.

For instance, in Figure 4.2, $\text{Refund} \in \mathcal{D}$ with $\text{Consumer}, \text{Business}, \text{Item} \in \mathcal{R}$.

Notice that descriptions can be used as roles as well. For instance, $\text{Customer care policy} = (\text{Commerce buy}, \text{Refund}, \text{Reason}) \in \mathcal{D}$, where $\text{Commerce buy}, \text{Refund} \in \mathcal{D}$.

Definition 2. A situation s is a tuple $s = (e_1, \dots, e_n) \in \mathcal{S}$ with $e_i \in \mathcal{D} \cup \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{E} \cup \mathcal{S}$.

For example, the tuple $(\text{Bob}, \text{ENCOM}, \text{Laptop})$ of Figure 4.2 is a situation.

A situation can also involve other situations as its entities. For example, in Figure 4.2, the tuple

$$s = ((\text{ENCOM}, \text{Alice}, \text{Laptop}), \\ (\text{Alice}, \text{ENCOM}, \text{Laptop}), \\ \text{BatteryDefect})$$

represents a situation in which *Alice* bought a *Laptop* from *ENCOM*, *ENCOM* received it back from *Alice* and a *BatteryDefect* reason is specified. Both *Alice* buying and *ENCOM* receiving the *Laptop* are two separate situations that are part of another situation, which also involves *BatteryDefect*.

When a description d explains a situation s , we say that s *satisfies* d , written as $d \models s$.

Definition 3 (satisfaction). With $d \in \mathcal{D}$ and $s \in \mathcal{S}$

$$d \models s \Leftrightarrow \forall r \in d. (\exists e \in s. e \in r) \vee (\exists s' \in s. r \models s')$$

In Figure 4.2 the situation $s = (\text{Bob}, \text{ENCOM}, \text{Laptop})$ satisfies the descriptions *Commerce buy* and *Contest winning*. Both descriptions are perspectives from which s can be interpreted. Assuming that $\mathcal{O}$ asserts that $\text{Consumer}, \text{Business} \subseteq \text{Agent}$ (i.e. *Agent* is a broader role than *Consumer* and *Business*), we have that *Commercial transaction* $\models s$ as well, since the two roles are also *Agents*.

Corollary 1. Given $d, d' \in \mathcal{D}$ with $d' \subseteq d$ and $s \in \mathcal{S}$ then $d' \models s \Rightarrow d \models s$.

³In the original formalization of DnS this is called maximal satisfaction. Our formalization is able to capture all possible types of satisfaction although the terminology is simplified.

Proof to Corollary 1 trivially follows from definition 3.

Definition 3 states the condition such that a perspective is valid for a situation. However, a description can be a plausible perspective for a situation even if only some of its roles are fulfilled. In this case, we say that a description *nearly* satisfies a situation, written as $d \tilde{\models} s$.

Definition 4 (*near-satisfaction*). With $d \in \mathcal{D}$ and $s \in \mathcal{S}$,

$$d \tilde{\models} s \Leftrightarrow \exists r \in d. (\exists e \in s. e \in r) \vee (\exists s' \in s. r \models s')$$

From Definition 4 it follows that if a situation satisfies a description, then it also *nearly*-satisfies it.

Corollary 2. With $d \in \mathcal{D}$ and $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $d \models s \Rightarrow d \tilde{\models} s$

The proof is trivial and follows from Definitions 3 and 4.

4.4 Methodology

This section describes the methodology used in *sandra*. Proof of theorems are omitted but are available in [55]. We define a vector space V over the field $\mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{D}|}$. For each description $d \in \mathcal{D}$ a subspace V_d is identified by its roles. Assuming that $\mathbf{v}_s$ is a vector representing $s \in \mathcal{S}$ and that $d \models s$ with $d \in \mathcal{D}$, the intuition following from Definition 3 (and 4) is that $\mathbf{v}_s$ must be defined by (some) entities classified by the roles in $\mathcal{D}$ that identify the subspace V_d .

In this section, we describe how a subspace V_d is defined and how to deduce when a description is (*nearly*-)satisfied by a situation. Notation-wise, we assume that $s \in \mathcal{S}$ and for some $d \in \mathcal{D}$, V_d is the subspace associated with d and B_d is the spanning set (span) of V_d .

4.4.1 Subspace definition

The set B_d , defined as $B_d = \{\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_n\}$ is a basis for the subspace V_d , i.e. the vectors in B_d form a minimal spanning set for V_d . Hence every $\mathbf{v} \in V_d$ can be expressed as a linear combination (a weighted sum) of the vectors in B_d [78].

Given Definitions 3 and 4, it follows that the vectors in B_d must originate from the description d and its roles $r \in d$. We define $\mathbf{f}_d$ as the function that converts each description $d \in \mathcal{D}$ to a vector $\mathbf{f}_d(d) \in B_d$. Informally, $\mathbf{f}_d(d)$ is obtained by recursively aggregating the vector representations $\mathbf{v}_r$ of the roles $r \in d$. A function ϕ computes $\mathbf{v}_r$ ensuring that $\mathbf{f}_d(d) \in B_d$ and that $\mathbf{v}_r$ reflects subsumption relations between roles.

Definition 5 ($\mathbf{f}_d$). Given $d \in \mathcal{D}$, the function $\mathbf{f}_d : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow V$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{f}_d(d) = \sum_{r \in d} \begin{cases} \mathbf{f}_d(r) & \text{if } r \in \mathcal{D} \\ [\phi(r, x_1) \parallel \dots \parallel \phi(r, x_n)] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $x_i \in \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{D}$ and $\phi : (\mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{D}) \times (\mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{D}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $\phi(x, y) = \mathbb{1}_{[x \subseteq y]}$

Proposition 1 (f_d is bijective). With $d \in \mathcal{D}$ and $\alpha, \beta \in V$

$$f_d(d) = \alpha \wedge f_d(d) = \beta \Leftrightarrow \alpha = \beta$$

Proposition 2 (f_d is a linear function). With $d \in \mathcal{D}, \alpha \in \mathbb{R}$

$$\alpha f_d(d) = f_d(\alpha d)$$

Theorem 1. Given a description $d \in \mathcal{D}$, the set $B = \{f_d(r_1), \dots, f_d(r_n)\}$ with $r_1, \dots, r_n \in d$ is composed of linearly independent vectors and forms a basis for the subspace V_d .

It follows that we can find the spanning set B_d (and hence V_d) of any description d within the ontology $\mathcal{O}$ as $B_d = \{f_d(r_1), \dots, f_d(r_n)\}$ for all $r_i \in d$.

We assume, without any loss of generality, that $\mathcal{O}$ can be represented as an acyclic directed graph. It follows from Definition 5 that for any $d \in \mathcal{D}$, B_d can be computed in polynomial time $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{D}|^2)$. The proof follows from Definition 5: in the worst case for each description we have to loop through every other description.

4.4.2 Situation encoding

Given the definition of the subspace V_d , the intuition is that its vectors are those representing all the situations s such that $d \models s$. To obtain $v_s \in V$, the vector representation of s , we introduce the function f_s , which maps a situation $s \in \mathcal{S}$ into a vector.

Definition 6. Given $s \in \mathcal{S}, e \in \mathcal{E}$ and $r \in \mathcal{R}$, and with $\psi : \mathcal{E} \rightarrow \mathcal{R}$ defined such that $e \in r \Rightarrow \psi(e) = r$, the function $f_s : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow V$ is defined as

$$f_s(s) = \sum_{e \in s} \begin{cases} f_s(e) & \text{if } e \in \mathcal{S} \\ f_d(\psi(e)) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The function ψ can be implemented by a deductive reasoner (e.g. [79]) or provided externally.

The vector v_s produced by the function f_s is the aggregation of the vector representation of the roles that classifies the entities in s and its nested situations. Nested situations are recursively converted into a vector using the same function f_s . Note that f_s is a positive definite function, i.e. $f_s(x) \geq 0 \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$. This follows directly from ϕ in Definition 5.

4.4.3 Description satisfaction

Given Theorem 1 and function f_s , we can check whether the vector representation v_s lies in the subspace V_d by checking whether v_s is a linear combination of the vectors in B_d .

Consider A_d as the $|\mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{D}| \times |d|$ matrix whose column-space is B_d (i.e. the columns are formed by all the vectors $\mathbf{b} \in B_d$). The solution $\mathbf{x}$ to the linear system $A_d \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{v}_s$ contains the coefficients to obtain the vector $\mathbf{v}_s$ as the linear combination of the vectors $\mathbf{b} \in B_d$. Since the columns of A_d are linearly independent by definition, it follows that $\text{rank}(A_d) = |d|$. The solution $\mathbf{x}$ is unique and can be computed as $\mathbf{x} = A_d^+ \mathbf{v}_s$ where A_d^+ is the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of A_d [78].

If $x_i \neq 0$ for all $x_i \in \mathbf{x}$ then $\mathbf{v}_s$ can be expressed as a linear combination of the vectors in B_d meaning that $\mathbf{v}_s \in V_d$. Since B_d is directly defined after the roles of d (Definition 5), then the roles of d must classify the entities in s . Based on this, we define how to deduce the descriptions satisfied by s according to Definition 3.

Theorem 2. Given $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $d \in \mathcal{D}$, and $\mathbf{v}_s = \mathbf{f}_s(s)$ we have that

$$d \models s \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{v}_s \in V_d$$

4.4.4 P-sandra (Probabilistic sandra)

According to Theorem 2 each element of the vector $\mathbf{x}$ (with $\mathbf{x} = A_d^+ \mathbf{v}_s$) indicates the presence (or absence) of an entity $e \in s$ with $e \in r$ and $r \in d$. By applying the Heaviside function $\mathbb{1}_{[>0]}$ to $\mathbf{x}$ we can interpret it as a boolean vector.

We model the satisfaction of a description as a multinomial probability distribution, hence the probability that s satisfies d is

$$p(d \models s) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{|d|} \mathbb{1}_{[>0]}(\mathbf{x})_i}{|d|} \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 7. Given $d \in \mathcal{D}$, $s \in \mathcal{S}$ and A_d the matrix whose column-space is B_d , we say that s nearly-satisfies d with probability $\hat{p}$, written as $d \stackrel{\sim}{\models}_{\hat{p}} s$, if $p(d \models s) = \hat{p}$.

Given Definition 7, we can now state Theorem 3, which generalizes Theorem 2 to nearly-satisfied descriptions according to Definition 4.

Theorem 3. With $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $d \in \mathcal{D}$ then $d \stackrel{\sim}{\models}_{\hat{p}} s \Rightarrow d \stackrel{\sim}{\models} s$ with $\hat{p} = p(d \models s) > 0$; $d \stackrel{\sim}{\models}_1 s \Rightarrow d \models s$; $d \stackrel{\sim}{\models}_0 s \Rightarrow d \not\models s$.

Theorem 3 enables a crucial property of our formalization: to infer to which degree a description is satisfied by a situation, while retaining correctness with respect to Definitions 3 (satisfaction) and 4 (near-satisfaction).

4.4.5 *dP-sandra* (Differentiable *P-sandra*)

By virtue of Theorem 3, the process of deducing which descriptions are satisfied (or *nearly-satisfied*) by a situation is a function $H : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{D}|}$, with

$$H(s) = [p(d_1 \models s) \parallel \cdots \parallel p(d_n \models s)] \quad (4.2)$$

with $d_1, \dots, d_n \in \mathcal{D}$.

H is differentiable with respect to the input vector $\mathbf{v}_s$ (it is composition of differentiable functions) and in particular $\nabla H = [\delta(\mathbf{v}_s) \parallel \cdots \parallel \delta(\mathbf{v}_s)]$ where δ is Dirac's delta and $d_1, \dots, d_n \in \mathcal{D}$. Due to the use of the Heaviside function, the gradient is zero everywhere except for the descriptions with probability zero, since $\delta(x) = 0 \forall x \neq 0$. This prevents an effective use of H in Machine Learning methods that rely on gradients to learn the model's parameters, such as in Deep Learning, where the back-propagation algorithm is used [80].

To overcome this issue, we replace the Heaviside function $\mathbb{1}_{>0}(x)$ with the *ReLU* function [81]. We argue, without any loss in generality, that the behaviour of the *ReLU* function is comparable to the Heaviside function in our setting, since $ReLU(x) > 0 \Leftrightarrow x > 0$. Indeed, we can interpret the *ReLU* function as a smooth version of $\mathbb{1}_{>0}(x)$. Other functions could be used for the same purpose, such as continuous approximations of the Heaviside function, *tanh*, logistic function etc. In this case, we rely on *ReLU* since empirically it suffers less from the exploding/vanishing gradient problem. Nonetheless, we will perform a systematic assessment of other functions in the future, as different functions might lead to different useful properties.

4.4.6 Neuro-symbolic integration

Since *dP-sandra* is differentiable with respect to its input vector, it can be used as a standard neural network layer. We define the function $\tilde{H}$ by replacing the Heaviside function in H (as defined in Equation 4.2) with the *ReLU* function. The function $\tilde{H}$ allows a seamless integration of a DnS-based ontology $\mathcal{O}$ within any arbitrary neural network NN .

The NN approximates the function f_s . Given $\mathbf{x}$ a vector generated by a neural network, for instance the features extracted by a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) from an image or the embedding of a sentence computed by a Transformer, $f_s(\mathbf{x}) \in V$.

Hence, we can check if the situation represented by $\mathbf{x}$ satisfies d by relying on Definition 4.1. Moreover, since $\tilde{H}$ is fully differentiable with respect to its input, it is possible to define an objective function that optimizes the output of the NN such that the representation learned for $\mathbf{x}$ lies in V_d as if it was produced by f_s .

We highlight that our experiments [55] show that the representation learned by NN (a vector $\mathbf{x}$ originating from any source) the vector representation of a situation s manually curated for modeling or representing that source, such as in a Knowledge Graph. This provides us with a means to interpret the intermediate output of the NN , and better understand its internal representation, without influencing the process to solve the down-stream task. For example, given the recording of a compositions and a neural network solving the genre classification task, *sandra* infers all the

possible perspectives, represented by a musical theory, without compromising the freedom of the model to formulate the final prediction.

4.5 Music classification experiments

By relying on *sandra*, a musicological theory can be formalised using a DnS ontology and music compositions can be classified using it. From a representation point of view, such theories can be formalised using the Polifonia Ontology Network [82], particularly relying on the music representation module.

We experiment with two theories: roman numeral analysis [83] and cadences as defined by Zarlino [84]. Both theories are conflicting one with the other: they are traditionally used for very different type of compositions and have been formulated in different historical periods, where the concept of *tonality* had a different meaning.

4.5.1 Roman numeral classification

Roman numeral analysis is mostly used to analyse modern music composition, and it revolves around the idea of assigning to each note in a scale a numerical degree. For example, when taking into account a *major* scales, the chords built on the first degree are composed by a major triad. If we consider the scale of *C major*, then the chords that will be classified as first degree are all of those chords that are composed by a *C major* triad. We formalise 4 scales: *major scale*, *minor scale*, *harmonic minor scale* and *melodic minor scale*. Table 4.1 contains a detailed description of the triad quality of each degree.

Scale	Triad quality on degree						
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
Major	Maj	Min	Min	Maj	Maj	Min	Dim
Minor	Min	Dim	Maj	Min	Min	Maj	Maj
Harmonic Minor	Min	Dim	Aug	Min	Maj	Maj	Dim
Melodic Minor	Min	Min	Aug	Maj	Maj	Dim	Dim

Table 4.1: Triad quality for the specific degrees in a scale. Minor triad as written as *Min*, major as *Maj*, augmented as *Aug* and diminished as *Dim*.

We develop an DnS ontology that follows Table 4.1 and can be natively used within *sandra*. Each scale is formalized as a description while each scale's degree is defined as a role. For example, the `C Major Scale` description includes the role `C major`. Since Table 4.1 is only defined by relying on the quality of a triad (major, minor, etc) we simplify all the chords of a composition and only consider its triad.

In Table 4.2 the classification of a song extracted from ChoCo is reported. A set of possible scales, which constitute valid perspective from which the song can be interpreted, are reported.

Scale	Probability	Explanation
A Minor	0.57	III (C:maj), IV (D:min), VII (G:(3,5,b7)), I (A:min)
C Major	0.57	I (C:maj), II (D:min), V (G:(3,5,b7)), VI (A:min)
G Major	0.428	IV (C:maj), I (G:(3,5,b7)), II (A:min)
F Major	0.428	V (C:maj), VI (D:min), III (A:min)
D Minor	0.428	VII (C:maj), I (D:min), V (A:min)
E Minor	0.428	VI (C:maj), III (G:(3,5,b7)), VI (A:min)
A Harmonic Minor	0.33	IV (D:min), I (A:min)
D Melodic Minor	0.33	I (D:min), IV (G:(3,5,b7))
E Harmonic Minor	0.33	VI (C:maj), IV (A:min)
C Melodic Minor	0.33	II (D:min), V (G:(3,5,b7))
G Melodic Minor	0.33	IV (C:maj), II (A:min)
F Melodic Minor	0.16	V (C:maj)
C Harmonic Minor	0.16	V (G:(3,5,b7))
C Flat Harmonic Minor	0.16	VI (G:(3,5,b7))
F Harmonic Minor	0.16	V (C:maj)
C Harmonic Minor	0.16	V (G:(3,5,b7))
D Harmonic Minor	0.16	I (D:min)
A Melodic Minor	0.16	I (A:min)
B Harmonic Minor	0.16	VI (G:(3,5,b7))
B Minor	0.14	VI (G:(3,5,b7))
D Major	0.14	IV (G:(3,5,b7))
G Minor	0.14	V (D:min)
B $\flat$ Major	0.14	III (D:min)

Table 4.2: Classification of the song *Capers* from ChoCo, composed by the chords *C:maj*, *D:min*, *G:7* and *A:min*. For each song an explanation for the classification is provided.

For each valid perspective, a probability computed and an explanation is provided by the method. The probability directly depends on the chords that are present within the song. The more the chord progression fits a specific description (such as in the *A minor* scale) the higher the probability. The explanation provides the motivations for a classification inferred. For instance, in the case of *A Minor*, the chord *C:maj* is considered as the third degree, while the *G:7* (*G:(3, 5, b7)*) as the seventh degree.

4.5.2 Cadence classification

Cadence classification, in the context of Zarlino's theory, refers to the classification of a music segment where a reference note and a target note are identified. Classifying a cadence is a fundamental step in understanding the modal attribution of a composition. Even though Zarlino's cadence classification is not directly suited to classify compositions extracted from ChoCo, we

provide here a straightforward formalization of it to demonstrate the possibilities when relying on a DnS ontology and *sandra*.

Reference note	Target notes
C	C, E, G
D	D, F, A
E	E, G, B
F	F, A, C
G	G, B, D
A	A, C, E
B $\flat$	B $\flat$, D, F

Table 4.3: Cadence classification rules as defined by Zarlino.

In Table 4.3 the rules that are used to classify a cadence are described. The rules can be seen as *if-then* conditions. For instance, if the reference note is *C* and the target note is *G* then the cadence takes the name of a *Regular C cadence on G*. Since ChoCo's compositions are formed by chords, we adapt the rules of Table 4.3 to classify chord sequences. In particular, we consider the root note of the first chord as the reference note and the root note of the last chord in the sequence as the target note.

Scale	Probability
Regular F Cadence on F	0.5
Regular E Cadence on G	0.5
Regular E Cadence E	0.5
Regular E Cadence B	0.5
Regular D Cadence F	0.5

Table 4.4: Classification of the song *It hurts me to* from ChoCo, composed by the chords *E:maj*, *A:maj*, *A:(3,5,b7)*, *B:maj*, *E:(3,5,b7)*, *B:(3,5,b7)*, *A:min*, *F:(3,5,b7)*. For each song an explanation for the classification is provided.

In Table 4.4 the classification of a song extracted from ChoCo is reported. A set of possible cadences, which constitute valid perspective from which the song can be interpreted, are reported. For each valid perspective, a probability is computed. The results of Table 4.4 demonstrate the flexibility of *sandra*. It is sufficient to formalise a theory using the DnS ontology design pattern to easily classify a chord sequence even though the theory is not directly designed for that scope. This can help uncovering hidden patterns in music compositions, particularly highlighting hidden aspects that are not traditionally taken into consideration.

4.6 FAIRness and reproducibility

Sandra is currently under review. As such, the code is currently accessible through an anonymized repository at the URL <https://anonymous.4open.science/r/sandra-C3D3/>. The code will be release openly once the review process ends and a Zenodo release will be performed.

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